

Species 1: *H. melpomene*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.82; high PNT

NOT test

Species 2: *H. cydno*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.61; high PNT

Environmental overlap

PC1

Red= $S1 > S2$, Blue= $S1 < S2$, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.333

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
 $D = 0.44$

D
p.value = 0.79242

Background 2→1

D
p.value = 0.00365

Background 1→2

D
p.value = 0.00257

Species 1: *H. melpomene*

NDT test

Species 2: *H. cydno*

Environmental overlap

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D= 0.49

Background 2->1

Background 1->2

